

Sentiment Analysis and Influence Tracking using Twitter

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Abstract— An overwhelming number of consumers are active in social media platforms. Within these platforms consumers are sharing their true feelings about a particular brand/product, its features, customer service and how it stands the competition. With the booming of microblogs on the Web, people have begun to express their opinions on a wide variety of topics on Twitter and other similar services. In a world where information can bias public opinion it is essential to analyse the propagation and influence of information in large-scale networks. Recent research studying social media data to rank users by topical relevance have largely focused on the “retweet”, “following” and “mention” relations. We also perform linguistic analysis of the collected corpus and explain discovered phenomena. Using the corpus, we build a sentiment classifier, that is able to determine positive, negative and neutral sentiments for a document. This paper discusses how Twitter data is used as a corpus for analysis by the application of sentiment analysis and a study of different algorithms and methods that help to track influence and impact of a particular user/brand active on the social network.

Index Terms—Twitter, sentiment analysis, influence, People Rank, TwitterRank.

I. INTRODUCTION

Microblogging today has become a very popular communication tool among Internet users. Millions of messages are appearing daily in popular web-sites that provide services for microblogging such as Twitter, Tumblr, Facebook. Authors of those messages write about their life,

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share opinions on variety of topics and discuss current issues. Because of a free format of messages and an easy accessibility of microblogging platforms, Internet users tend to shift from traditional communication tools (such as traditional blogs or mailing lists) to microblogging services.

As more and more users post about products and services they use, or express their political and religious views, microblogging^[2] web- sites become valuable sources of people’s opinions and sentiments. Such data can be efficiently used for marketing or social studies. We use a dataset formed of collected messages from Twitter. Twitter contains a very large number of very short messages created by the users of this microblogging platform. The contents of the messages vary from personal thoughts to public statements.

As a microblogging and social networking website, Twitter has become very popular and has grown rapidly. An increasing number of people are willing to post their opinions on Twitter, which is now considered a valuable online source for opinions. As a result, sentiment analysis on Twitter is a rapid and effective way of gauging public opinion for business marketing or social studies. For example, a business can retrieve timely feedback on a new product in the market by evaluating people's opinions on Twitter. As people often talk about various entities (e.g., products, organizations, people, etc.) in a tweet, we perform sentiment analysis at the entity level; that is, we mine people's opinions on specific entities in each tweet rather than the opinion about each whole sentence or whole tweet. We assume that the entities are provided by the user, e.g., he/she is interested in opinions on iPhone (an entity).

In our paper, we study how microblogging can be used for sentiment analysis purposes. We show how to use Twitter as a corpus for sentiment analysis and opinion mining. We use microblogging and more particularly Twitter for the following reasons:

- Microblogging platforms are used by different people to express their opinion about different topics, thus it is a valuable source of people’s opinions.
- Twitter contains an enormous number of text posts and it grows every day. The collected corpus can be arbitrarily large.
- Twitter’s audience varies from regular users to celebrities, company representatives, politicians, and even country

presidents. Therefore, it is possible to collect text posts of users from different social and interests groups.

Sentiment is an attitude, thought, or judgment prompted by feeling. **Sentiment analysis** is the process of determining and measuring the tone, attitude, opinion, and emotional state of responses. More precisely, it is the concept of deciding whether a specific conversation is positive, negative, or neutral. Sentiment analysis has broad applications and encompasses work in classifying subjectivity, polarity, tonality, emotion mining, opinion mining, persuasion analysis, and affective computing. It is a tool that allows companies to analyze what their customers are saying regarding their products and services, and also monitor trends in the opinions and attitudes of their customers toward the products and services with respect to their competitors.

There are various types of marketing strategies such as mass marketing, segmentation and one to one marketing. One to one marketing is an effort to find individual customer's needs and to provide a good response for them. Recommender systems have appeared in e-commerce problems to support product recommendation, which provide one to one marketing. Indeed, recommender systems individualize the way of recommending products. These systems try to recommend different products to each customer with collecting data of customer preferences and data mining techniques. Recommender systems have recently become popular among many well-known e-businesses such as Amazon.com, MovieFinder.com.

As people often talk about various entities (e.g., products, organizations, people, etc.) in a tweet, we perform sentiment analysis at the entity level; that is, we mine people's opinions on specific entities in each tweet rather than the opinion about each whole sentence or whole tweet. We assume that the entities are provided by the user, e.g., he/she is interested in opinions on iPhone (an entity). One approach to perform sentiment analysis is based on a function of opinion words in context. Opinion words are words that are commonly used to express positive or negative sentiments, e.g., "good" and "bad". The approach generally uses a dictionary of opinion words to identify and determine sentiment orientation (positive, negative or neutral). The dictionary is called the opinion lexicon.

Twitter Data

Twitter has developed its own language conventions. The following are examples of Twitter conventions.

1. "RT" is an acronym for retweet, which is put in front of a tweet to indicate that the user is repeating or reposting.

2. "#" called the hashtag is used to mark, organize or alter tweets according to topics or categories.

3. "@username1" represents that a message is a reply to a user whose user name is username1".

4. Emoticons and colloquial expressions are frequently used in tweets, e.g. \:-)", lovvve", lmao".

5. External Web links (e.g. <http://amze.ly/8K4n0t>) are also commonly found in tweets to refer to some external sources.

6. Length: Tweets are limited to 140 characters. This is different from usual opinionated corpora such as reviews and blogs, which are usually long.

Another unique characteristic of Twitter data compared to the other opinionated corpora is its volume. It is estimated that people post about 60 million tweets every day and the number is still increasing rapidly.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection

Twitter has an open API that allows anyone to get a list of a user's friends (provided the account is not private) It is therefore easy to create a graph of the network. Since there are more than 100M nodes in this graph with many times that many edges, it requires a lot of computational power to process this entire graph. I therefore propose to focus on a smaller subset. However, recently Twitter has been more circumspect in allowing unfettered access to the entire social graph and tweet stream. It allows this access termed the "fire hose" to a small chosen set of companies only. Through the public API, one can only access a single user's tweet stream and his profile information and also the public timeline of tweets.

The Streaming API is the real-time sample of the Twitter Firehose. This API is for those developers with data intensive needs. If you're looking to build a data mining product or are interested in analytics research, the Streaming API is most suited for such things. Streaming API allows for large quantities of keywords to be specified and tracked, retrieving geo-tagged tweets from a certain region, or have the public statuses of a user set returned. This requires you to establish a long-lived HTTP connection and maintain that connection.

The Twitter Search API is a dedicated API for running searches against the real-time index of recent Tweets. If you're currently developing on the Search API, and find that your application is being rate-limited or you just have aggressive querying needs, then you should be moving over to the Streaming API.

B. Analysis

Using Twitter API we collected a corpus of text posts and formed a dataset of three classes: positive sentiments, negative sentiments, and a set of objective texts (no sentiments). We queried Twitter for two types of emoticons:

- Happy emoticons: “:-)”, “:)”, “=)”, “:D” etc.
- Sad emoticons: “:-(”, “:(”, “=(”, “:(” etc.

The two types of collected corpora will be used to train a classifier to recognize positive and negative sentiments. Because each message cannot exceed 140 characters by the rules of the microblogging platform, it is usually composed of a single sentence. Therefore, we assume that an emoticon within a message represents an emotion for the whole message and all the words of the message are related to this emotion.

i. Preparing the Data

The data set contains information on X million profiles. Profile information is limited to the user accounts followed by the user. Since the data set is as of a certain date, the information is not complete as of today. However, the data set contained enough information to create training and test data sets.

All the tweets would be initially considered as a bag of words.

for eg. "This is excellent"

would not be considered as a string but as a bag of three words "This", "is" and "excellent".

Then the stop words such as "the", "a", "with" etc will be removed from the bag as these words do not have any sentiment expressing nature. Once these non-sentimental stop words are removed and hence the corpus refined, the process of sentiment analysis can begin.

ii. Sentiment gradation

The bag of sentiment expressive words i.e. every tweet is now analyzed in parts. A knowledge base is created which has the relative sentiments of words denoted by a floating point number ranging from -1 to 1.

All the words in the bag are cross checked across this knowledge base. This gives the sentiment of every word in the range. After this, taking into consideration the type of words and their sentiment score, the sentiment of the overall tweet is calculated. This would determine what the sentiment of the tweet is and how the user has expressed his satisfaction over the product or service.

Classifications

Four classifications are used in this corpus:

Positive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive indicator on topic
Neutral	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neither positive nor negative indicators • Mixed positive and negative indicators • On topic, but indicator undeterminable • Simple factual statements • Questions with no strong emotions indicated
Negative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negative indicator on topic
Irrelevant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not English language • Not on-topic (e.g. spam)

Sentiment assignment is an extremely subjective exercise.

For this corpus, “Positive” and “Negative” labels were reserved for tweets which clearly express an emotion or where the implications were unambiguous. As a rule of thumb, “neutral” was the preferred label for border line cases.

Examples:

There are huge lines at the @apple store.

Labeled **neutral**. From a shoppers perspective this could be bad, or it could be a sign of excitement about the product launch. From an investor’s perspective this could be good, since it indicates a strong new product launch.

I had to wait for six friggin’ hours in line at the @apple store.

Labeled **negative**. The tweeter is clearly unhappy with the situation and is referring to Apple in the negative sense.

iii. Preprocessing

Data preprocessing consists of three steps: 1) tokenization, 2) normalization, and 3) part-of-speech (POS) tagging.^[12]

Emoticons and abbreviations (e.g., OMG, WTF, BRB) are identified as part of the tokenization process and treated as individual tokens.

For the normalization process, the presence of abbreviations within a tweet is noted and then abbreviations are replaced by their actual meaning (e.g., BRB -> be right back). We also identify informal intensifiers such as all-caps (e.g., I LOVE this show!!! and character repetitions (e.g., I’ve got a mortgage!! happyyyyyy”), note their presence in the tweet. All-caps words are made into lowercase, and instances of repeated characters are replaced by a single character.

Finally, the presence of any special Twitter tokens is noted (e.g., #hashtags, usertags, and URLs) and placeholders indicating the token type are substituted. Our hope is that this normalization improves the performance of

the POS tagger, which is the last preprocessing step.

iv. Feature-based extraction

The collected dataset is used to extract features that will be used to train our sentiment classifier. We used the presence of an n-gram as a binary feature, while for general information retrieval purposes, the frequency of a keyword's occurrence is a more suitable feature, since the overall sentiment may not necessarily be indicated through the repeated use of keywords.

A. Process of constructing n-grams

1. Filtering – we remove URL links (e.g. <http://example.com>), Twitter user names (e.g. @alex – with symbol @ indicating a user name), Twitter special words (such as “RT”), and emoticons.
2. Tokenization – we segment text by splitting it by spaces and punctuation marks, and form a bag of words. However, we make sure that short forms such as “don't”, “I'll”, “she'd” will remain as one word.
3. Removing stopwords – we remove articles (“a”, “an”, “the”) from the bag of words.
4. Constructing n-grams – we make a set of n-grams out of consecutive words. A negation (such as “no” and “not”) is attached to a word which precedes it or follows it. For example, a sentence “I do not like fish” will form two bigrams: “I do+not”, “do+not like”, “not+like fish”. Such a procedure allows to improve the accuracy of the classification since the negation plays a special role in an opinion and sentiment expression.

1. Unigram

Building the unigram model took special care because the Twitter language model is very different from other domains from past research. The unigram feature extractor addressed the following issues:

- a. Tweets contain very **casual language**. For example, you can search “hungry” with a random number of u's in the middle of the word on <http://search.twitter.com> to understand this. Here is an example sampling:
huuuungrly: 17 results in the last day
huuuuuungrly: 4 results in the last day
huuuuuuuungrly: 1 result in the last day
Besides showing that people are hungry, this emphasizes the casual nature of Twitter and the disregard for correct spelling.
- b. **Usage of links**. Users very often include links in their tweets. An equivalence class was created for all URLs. That is, a URL like “<http://tinyurl.com/cvvg9a>” was converted to the symbol “URL.”

c. **Usernames**. Users often include usernames in their tweets, in order to address messages to particular users. A de facto standard is to include the @ symbol before the username (e.g. @alecmgo). An equivalence class was made for all words that started with the @ symbol.

d. **Removing the query term**. Query terms were stripped out from Tweets, to avoid having the query term affect the classification.

2. Bigrams

The reason we experimented with bigrams was we wanted to smooth out instances like 'not good' or 'not bad'. When negation as an explicit feature didn't help, we thought of experimenting with bigrams.

B. Negate as a features

NEGATE is added as a specific feature which is added when “not” or ‘n’t’ are observed in the dataset^[7]

C. Part of Speech (POS) features

We felt like POS tags would be a useful feature since how you made use of a particular word. For example, ‘over’ as a verb has a negative connotation whereas ‘over’ as the noun, would refer to the cricket over which by itself doesn't carry any negative or positive connotation.

D. Lexicon features

Words listed the MPQA subjectivity lexicon (Wilson, Wiebe, and Hoffmann 2009) are tagged with their prior polarity: positive, negative, or neutral. We create three features based on the presence of any words from the lexicon.

iv. Literature Review on taggers

The models included for sentiment analysis in our paper can be downloaded for the POS tagger website at <http://nlp.stanford.edu/software/tagger.shtml>. All taggers are accompanied by the props files used to create them, given below is a more detailed information about the creation of the taggers.

For English, the bidirectional taggers are slightly more accurate, but tag much more slowly; choose the appropriate tagger based on your speed/performance needs.

English taggers

wsj-0-18-bidirectional-distsim.tagger

Trained on WSJ sections 0-18 using a bidirectional architecture and including word shape and distributional similarity features.

Penn Treebank tagset.

Performance:

97.28% correct on WSJ 19-21

(90.46% correct on unknown words)

wsj-0-18-left3words.tagger

Trained on WSJ sections 0-18 using the left3words architecture and includes word shape features. Penn tagset.

Performance:

96.97% correct on WSJ 19-21

(88.85% correct on unknown words)

wsj-0-18-left3words-distsim.tagger

Trained on WSJ sections 0-18 using the left3words architecture and includes word shape and distributional similarity features. Penn tagset.

Performance:

97.01% correct on WSJ 19-21

(89.81% correct on unknown words)

english-left3words-distsim.tagger

Trained on WSJ sections 0-18 and extra parser training data using the left3words architecture and includes word shape and distributional similarity features. Penn tagset.

english-bidirectional-distsim.tagger

Trained on WSJ sections 0-18 using a bidirectional architecture and including word shape and distributional similarity features.

Penn Treebank tagset.

wsj-0-18-caseless-left3words-distsim.tagger

Trained on WSJ sections 0-18 left3words architecture and includes word shape and distributional similarity features.

Penn tagset. Ignores case.

english-caseless-left3words-distsim.tagger

Trained on WSJ sections 0-18 and extra parser training data using the left3words architecture and includes word shape and distributional similarity features. Penn tagset. Ignores case.

v. Inferring Edge Strength

In the simplest setting, a user being connected to another user can be used as a preference signal. In recent times, given the explosive growth of twitter, there have emerged a large number of "bot" accounts that seek to follow as many users as possible in the hope that unwitting users will follow them back. Therefore, looking at "followed" accounts yields more information about the account holder's preferences rather than "follower" accounts.

In a traditional item recommendation setting, users rate items on a scale of 1-5 or by an up or down vote. In twitter, there is no explicit rating of accounts by other users. However, we can construct some implicit signals from the user's content stream that are analogous to recommendation. Specifically, I look at three signals that are counted as up votes. First, if a user follows another account, that is considered a positive rating for the account that is followed. Second, if a user retweets (i.e. echoes a tweet to his own tweet stream), that can also be considered a positive rating. Thirdly, if a user shares a "hashtag" with another user, that is considered a positive rating for the user who is being followed. Sharing a hashtag

implies that the two tweets are related to the same topic, although they may express two entirely different opinions (for e.g. the recent controversy around wikileaks elicited a storm of either vehement approval or disapproval from twitter users, but they used the same #wikileaks hashtag).

III. ALGORITHMS

B. PeopleRank Algorithm

In general, global knowledge of network topology can make for very efficient routing and forwarding decisions. Collecting and exchanging topology information in opportunistic networks is cumbersome because of their intermittent connectivity and unpredictable mobility.

PeopleRank is inspired by the PageRank^[5] algorithm employed by Google to rank web pages. By crawling the entire web, this algorithm measures the relative importance of a page within a graph (web). Motivated by the success of this algorithm, we propose to apply a similar technique, which we call *PeopleRank* to rank the nodes in a social graph. The main idea is that nodes with a higher *PeopleRank* value will generally be more "central" in the social graph.

a. Centralized Peoplerank

In *PeopleRank* we tag people as "important" when they are linked (in a social context) to many other "important" people. We assume that only neighbors in the social graph have an impact of the popularity.

a social graph $G_s = (V_s, E_s)$ as a finite undirected graph with a vertex set V and an edge set E_s . An edge $(u, v) \in E_s$ if, and only if, there is a social relation between nodes u and v . In this paper, we define a social relationship between two nodes u and v either (i) if they are declared friends, or (ii) if they are sharing k common interests.

b. Distributed PeopleRank

The distributed version of *PeopleRank* is shown in Algorithm. In this version, whenever two neighbor nodes in the social graph meet, they exchange two pieces of information:

- (i) their current *PeopleRank* values; and
 - (ii) the number of social graph neighbors they have.
- Then, the two neighbors update their *PeopleRank* values

C. TwitterRank

TwitterRank measures the influence taking both the topical similarity between users and the link structure into account.

In a dataset prepared for this study, it is observed that 1)72.4% of the users follow more than 80% of their *followers*, and (2) 80.5% of the user have 80% of their *friends* follow them back.^[4]Our study reveals that the presence of “reciprocity” can be explained by phenomenon of homophily. Based on this finding, TwitterRank, an extension of PageRank algorithm, is proposed to measure the influence of users in Twitter. TwitterRank measures the influence taking both the topical similarity between users and the link structure into account. Experimental results show that TwitterRank outperforms the one Twitter currently uses and other related algorithms, including the original PageRank and Topic-sensitive PageRank.

First, it potentially brings order to the real-time web in that it allows the search results to be sorted by the authority/influence of the contributing twitterers giving a timely update of the thoughts of influential twitterers. Second, Twitter is also a marketing platform. Targeting those influential users will increase the efficiency of the marketing campaign. For example, a handphone manufacturer can engage those twitterers influential in topics about IT gadgets to potentially influence more people. There are also applications that utilize Twitter to gather opinions and information on particular topics. Identifying influential twitterers for interesting topics can improve the quality of opinions gathered.

PageRank improves over in-degree by considering the link structure of the whole network. Nevertheless, Pagerank ignores the interests of twitterers, which affects the way twitterers influence one another. Our proposed approach addresses the shortcomings of in-degree and PageRank by taking into account both the link structure and topical similarity among twitterers.

In the context of Twitter, homophily implies that a twitterer follows a friend because she is interested in some topics the friend is publishing, and the friend follows back because she finds they share similar topical interest.

C. Influence Tracking

In many ways Twitter-based marketing is like a pyramid scheme. While sending tweets to your own followers is one way of broadcasting a message, it is more effective to have others repeat your message either through literal retweets or more subtle gestures, such as replies and repeating the URLs that you tweet. If someone on Twitter receives your message through a trusted intermediary, it is assigned a much greater level of trust. So the goal is to get influential people to follow you and then act as a conduit for your marketing.^[10]

Influence is a sophisticated measure of a user’s relative importance among the entire Twitter network.

Uses various statistics about a handle as parameters like number of followers, retweets, mentions, URL’s shared.

There are three major components that add up to the score: your followers, your mentions and retweets, and your lists, all accounted as ratios between you and others.

Followers is the strongest component of the calculation is the number of followers you have. In my opinion, your presence on Twitter and getting followers can be influenced by at least the following three major factors concerning you and your Twitter account:

- i. *Persona* – how known you are. Measured by the number of followers you have, our time on Twitter.
- ii. *Engagement* – how engaged you are. Measured by the number of followers you have, compared the number of people you follow; Measured by the number of followers you have, compared to the number of mentions and retweets you’ve made.
- iii. *Wits* – how smart and creative your tweets are. Measured by the number of followers you have compared to the total number of tweets you've made.

For this part, the followers/following ratio the weight of 3, the followers/tweets a weight of 2 and the followers/time a weight of 1. The followers/(mentions + retweets) has a weight of 0.5 and works in the negative way, so people who bother other people get a bit of a minus to their followers result. Besides, those who are able to get the same number of followers without mentioning people, must have a small advantage.

The second most important part of the calculation is the ratio between mentions and being mentioned, together with the number of retweets you get with the absolute “reach” of those retweets (measured in the number of people who follow people that retweeted you). A similar reach is also accounted in the mentions and replies.

Twitter lists are getting used more and more, so they are also considered in the calculation. The number of lists you appear on, the number of people who follow those lists and the number of people, who follow lists you've created are the basic parameters for the calculation. This component adds only a small bit to the final score.

The three major components currently have the following weight in the final score:

- Followers: around 60%
- Mentions and retweets: around 30%
- Lists: around 10%

D. Model for calculating influence

The assumptions about the model:

1. Influence(X) = Expected number of people who will read a tweet that X tweets, including all retweets of that tweet. For simplicity, we assume that, if a person reads the same message twice (because of retweets), both readings count.

2. If X is a member of Followers(Y), then there is a $1/|Following(X)|$ probability that X will read a tweet posted by Y, where Following(X) is the set of people that X follows.

3. If X reads a tweet from Y, there's a constant probability p that X will retweet it.

This model is obviously simplistic in all three assumptions. But it's a reasonable first cut. In particular, it accounts for the inflation that occurs from people who follow in the hopes of reciprocity. There's less value in being followed by someone who follows a lot of people, because that person is less likely to read your messages or retweet them.

Of course, there's room for adding more realism to this model, but it is at least close enough to the truth to be interesting.

From this model, it's easy to measure someone's influence recursively, assuming that we know the constant retweet probability p:

$$Influence(X) = \sum_{Y \in Followers(X)} (1+p * Influence(Y)) / |Following(Y)|$$

IV. CONCLUSION

Microblogging nowadays became one of the major types of the communication. A recent research has identified it as online word-of-mouth branding. The era of analysis paralysis is officially over. Instead of just listening, companies can now study people and their interests based on what they say and do and also how they color their profiles.

This goldmine of insight gives brands the potential to improve marketing, promotional and advertising campaigns to start. As this practice develops, brands can also gather the intelligence necessary, and widely available, to improve products, services, and spark new waves of tweets gushing with positive sentiment. Doing so over time helps to build the social, and more relevant, business of the future while improving relationships to convert followers into stakeholders.

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Some publications:

1. Paper on 'Grid FTP Protocol combined with Data Grid use for sharing files' – Published in 'ETCC-08 - National Conference on emerging trends in Computing & Communication' at NIT, Hamirpur (30-31 Dec 2008)
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